

Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems

D7.2 SYNERGIES platform release v1

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Primary Author(s) Laura Rodriguez Llanza | IDIADA
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CONTRIBUTORS

Name	Organization	Name	Organization
Laura Rodriguez	IDIADA		
Fabio Corona	AVL		
Irene Saco	CTAG		
Sara Garcia	MOSAIC		

FORMAL REVIEWERS

Name	Organization	Date
Emmanuel ARNOUX	Renault	10/11/2025
Marc Perez	IDIADA	28/11/2025

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Platform Report (D7.2) provides a comprehensive overview of the SYNERGIES Platform as of its first release, showcasing the platform's current results and capabilities.

Building on the technical foundations defined in deliverable D7.1 (*Platform architecture and design together with the defined system components*), this document focuses on demonstrating the functionality of the first release of the platform from a user-oriented perspective, highlighting achievements and alignment with project objectives.

In addition, the document defines the roadmap towards the final releases, showcasing how the platform enables interoperability, reusability, and scalability of virtual testing tools for automated driving technologies. It serves as a reference for stakeholders across research, industry, and policy domains within the CCAM ecosystem.

Keywords: Platform, Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM), Virtual testing, Simulation, Scenarios, datasets, Automated Driving System.

2 SYNERGIES PLATFORM

The **SYNERGIES platform** is the key element to achieve the overall objective of the project; to accelerate the scenario-based or data-based development, virtual testing, validation, and homologation of Automated Driving Systems (ADS) by providing a harmonised, open and scalable digital infrastructure and by allowing the interoperability between already existing European scenario databases.

The following section provides a description of the platform's intended audience, current structure, the key components of the integrated system, and its usability.

2.1 Introduction and Intended audience

The platform has been designed as an interoperable, scalable and user-oriented environment that allows the sharing and reuse of scenarios, the integration of simulation tools and the execution of validation / homologation workflows adapted to different profiles. Its modular design and open architecture facilitate collaboration between various actors in the CCAM ecosystem, from manufacturers and technology providers to public authorities and their technical services, research centres and innovative companies.

The SYNERGIES Platform provides a unified digital environment to support scenario-based development and testing of CCAM systems. It enables partners, researchers, and industry users to manage, execute, and analyse large-scale simulations and data workflows across synthetic and real-world scenarios.

The intended audience includes researchers, developers, CCAM system integrators, CCAM system deployers, scenario providers, simulation platform developers, regulatory bodies and policymakers interested in innovative approaches to virtual validation and data-driven mobility research. Figure 1. SYNERGIES Platform intended audience shows the intended audience of the SYNERGIES platform

Figure 1. SYNERGIES Platform intended audience

2.2 Contribution to objectives

Based on the foundations laid out in deliverable D7.1 (related to *Platform Architecture and System Components*) and in line with the expectations of stakeholders defined in D2.1 (related to *Stakeholder high-level requirements*), the platform addresses the technical and operational objectives of SYNERGIES and contributes directly to the expected results.

The SYNERGIES Platform contributes to the following objectives:

- Provide accessible and harmonised scenarios through a federated Scenario Dataspace.
- Ensure interoperability, acceptance, and scalability by building upon the federated framework developed in the SUNRISE project.
- Guarantee safe, robust, and reliable platform operation through systematic testing, risk management, and continuous improvement.
- Facilitate data sharing and orchestration across partners and test facilities.
- Connect simulation environments for CCAM validation.
- To achieve this objective, WP7 will integrate and deliver the Scenario Dataspace in 3 different releases of the SYNERGIES Platform (D7.2-4). This first release is based on the federated framework developed in SUNRISE ([Sunrise Project | Developing and providing a harmonized and scalable CCAM Safety Assurance Framework](#)).

The objectives of the first platform release (D7.2) are:

- Functional platform running end-to-end.
- Connection to a database with real data.
- At least various scenarios are available and accessible through the platform.
- Integration of at least 5 tools into the Marketplace.
- Initial documentation aligned with Task 7.4.

2.3 Platform access

This section describes how to access the SYNERGIES Platform for the first release.

Step 1 – Go to the SYNERGIES Webpage

Open your web browser and go to the official project website:

<https://synergies-ccam.eu/>

Once on the homepage, click on “Platform” in the top navigation menu (Figure 2). This will redirect you to the SYNERGIES Platform application.

Figure 2. Accessing the Platform from the SYNERGIES website

Step 2 – Access the Platform

After clicking "Platform," the browser will automatically open the web application at:

<https://app.synergies-ccam.eu/>

The Sign-In page will appear on screen (Figure 3).

Figure 3. SYNERGIES Platform Sign-In Page

Step 3 – Log In (First Release Credentials)

For this first release, the registration process has been simplified.

Individual user registration and email verification are temporarily disabled to ensure smooth access during the demo phase.

Please use the following shared credentials to log in:

- Username: user1@vicomtech.org
- Password: User1234)

Step 4 – Navigate the Platform

Once logged in, users can explore the main sections of the SYNERGIES Platform (Figure 4):

- Dataspace: Browse, view, and interact with available scenario data.
- Marketplace: Discover tools, datasets, and services shared within the SYNERGIES ecosystem.
- Documentation: Access technical guides, user manuals, and platform documentation.
- SCDB Manager: View available Scenario Databases (SCDBs), check their connection status, and manage access.

Figure 4. Main dashboard and navigation menu

Next Release (Planned Update)

In future releases, the user registration and authentication system will be reactivated, allowing:

- Individual user accounts and email confirmation
- Secure role-based access control
- Personalized workspaces and saved preferences

2.4 Platform structure

As commented before; To achieve this objective, WP7 will integrate and deliver the Scenario Dataspace in 3 different releases of the SYNERGIES Platform. This first release is based on the federated framework developed in SUNRISE (Figure 5).

Figure 5. SUNRISE framework

At its core, SYNERGIES integrates two main components:

- **Scenario Dataspace:** A federated environment that provides access to harmonized real-world and synthetic driving scenarios from multiple sources. This dataspace enables stakeholders to access, share, and reuse scenarios in a standardized format, fostering collaboration and reducing duplication of effort.
- **Marketplace:** A service-oriented environment for sharing datasets and tools developed within the project or third parties. It provides comprehensive functionalities including data pre- and post-processing capabilities, advanced scenario generation tools, AI-enhanced analysis and processing, and governance and compliance tools.

The SYNERGIES Platform contains the following menus:

- **HOME** → Main page with general information about the platform, latest updates, news, and quick access to key features. It serves as the entry point for all users.

<https://app.synergies-ccam.eu/app>

- **USER REGISTRATION** → Secure interface for new users to create an account, Password must fulfil security criteria. Additionally, possible is for the users to manage their profile, and request access to specific tools or datasets based on their stakeholder role.

<https://app.synergies-ccam.eu/profile>

- **DATASPACE** → Detailed information about the federated scenario dataspace, including access to harmonised scenario repositories, metadata, usage guidelines, and tools for searching, uploading, and reusing CCAM-related scenarios.

<https://app.synergies-ccam.eu/query>

- **MARKETPLACE** → A service-oriented environment offering access to simulation tools, validation services, datasets, and certification frameworks. Users can browse, select, and integrate resources into their validation workflows.
<https://app.synergies-ccam.eu/marketplace>
- **DOCUMENTATION** → Centralised repository of technical documentation, user guides, API references, and training materials to support onboarding and effective use of the platform. Starting with versions V2 and V3, it will include handbooks and guides.
<https://app.synergies-ccam.eu/documentation>

Figure 6 shows an overview of the platform's architecture. The main functions continue the work of the previous Sunrise project. Synergies will then build on the existing structure to enhance the platform with new capabilities that were before not implemented.

Figure 6. Final Platform's architecture

2.5 Visual interface

Screenshots of the pages are included below.

The user is first required to create an account. Required data are name, surname, email and password. The password must fulfil a criteria, shown below in Figure 7.

Sign Up

Password does not meet the required criteria. Please ensure it meets all the requirements.

Name: fabio Surname: corona

Email: fabio.corona@avl.com

Password: Synergies2025 Confirm Password:

At least 8 characters long
Contain one uppercase letter
Contain one lowercase letter
Contain one number
Contain one special character
(e.g., ^\$*.[]{}?~!"@#%&\/><:;|_~'+=)

I agree with the [Terms & Conditions](#) ✓

Sign Up Already have an account? [Sign In](#)

Figure 7. User account creation

After creating an account, the user can sign via the page shown in Figure 8. Login and Sign-up. After a successful log-in, the user can then manage his/her profile in the corresponding section, shown in Figure 9. Profile manager section.

 SYNERGIES

Sign In

Email: Enter your email

Password: Enter your password

[Forgot Password?](#)

Sign In Don't have an account? [Sign Up](#)

Figure 8. Login and Sign-up

Figure 9. Profile manager section

From this page, it is then possible to connect to a specific scenario database. The list of possibilities is user-dependent. An example list and API entry request is given below in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

SCDB CONFIGURATION

Manage SCDB

AVAILABLE SCDBS			
Status	Name	Description	Actions
●	Streetwise	TNO Streetwise Scenario Database	+ Connect
●	DEMOSCDB2	SNew version of Demo SCDB	+ Connect
●	Scenius	AVL Scenius Scenario Database	+ Connect
●	AdScene	AdScene Scenario Database	+ Connect

Figure 10. List of databases that a user can connect to

Connect SCDB ✕

Connecting to: Scenius

Enter API Key

Submit API Key

Figure 11. For a specific database, an API key or other login type may be required

Once the user is connected to one or multiple databases, it can query them to obtain scenarios. The available queries can be accessed via the Query Manager, accessible in the Dataspace tab as shown in Figure 12. SYNERGIES Dataspace menu overview. By clicking on the Execute button, the query is transferred to the databases and the scenarios returned to the user as shown in Figure 13. SYNERGIES Dataspace: Scenarios. Additional queries can be created by clicking on the + button on the top-right corner of the Query Manager.

Figure 12. SYNERGIES Dataspace menu overview

Figure 13. SYNERGIES Dataspace: Scenarios

Clicking on any of the returned scenarios will display its information, such as the Scenario Type, Scenario Database that returned it, a Description, Entities, and OpenDRIVE/OpenSCENARIO files. An example of this visualization for a cut-in scenario is displayed in Figure 14. SYNERGIES Dataspace menu: Cut-in example.

Figure 14. SYNERGIES Dataspace menu: Cut-in example

On the marketplace tab, different applications can be found, as seen in Figure 15. SYNERGIES Marketplace menu.

Figure 15. SYNERGIES Marketplace menu

Finally, on the Documentation tab, there is a list of content including the Platform Overview, Marketplace documentation, Scenarios documentation, and Glossary; as shown in Figure 16. SYNERGIES Documentation menu.

The screenshot shows the SYNERGIES platform interface. At the top left is the SYNERGIES logo. The navigation bar includes 'Home', 'Dataspaces', 'Marketplace', and 'Documentation' (which is highlighted). A user profile 'Hi, User1 User1' is visible on the right. On the left, a 'Contents' sidebar lists 'Platform Overview', 'Marketplace', 'Scenarios', and 'Glossary' (which is selected). The main content area is titled 'Glossary' and lists 'Key Terms and Abbreviations' with definitions for various terms.

Key Terms and Abbreviations:	
Abstract Scenario	Formalized, declarative description derived from a functional scenario. The semantics of the description will be closely tied to an ontology, drastically increasing the precision of the employed terminology.
ADS (Automated Driving System)	A system that performs the entire dynamic driving task on a sustained basis.
CCAM (Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility)	Systems that enable vehicles to communicate with each other and infrastructure to improve safety and efficiency.
Concrete Scenario	Scenario depicted with explicit parameter values, describing physical attributes. Parameter values can consist of default values, randomly chosen values or advisedly chosen values.
Coverage	The extent that something (A) is addressed by something else (B).
Descriptor	A feature or attribute used to characterize an object or set of data, capturing essential information in a way that can be used for further analysis, comparison or classification.
Functional Scenario	Scenario described in natural language on a conceptual level, in general without specific physical values.
HMI (Human-Machine-Interface)	Interaction between the driver (or user) and the vehicle via input and output devices.
Logical Scenario	Scenario described with the inclusion of parameters, including the set of allowable parameter values and, optionally, the (possibly joint) distribution of the parameters.
ODD (Operational Design Domain)	Operating conditions under which a given driving automation system or feature thereof is specifically designed to function, including environmental, geographical, and time-of-day restrictions, and/or the

At the bottom of the page, there are logos for SYNERGIES and 'Funded by the European Union', along with links for 'About Us', 'Terms of Service', and 'Contact'.

Figure 16. SYNERGIES Documentation menu

3 REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

The requirements analysis has been concluded in WP2 task 2.1 and is used as input for this task ([D2.1 Stakeholder high-level requirements](#)). The following paragraphs group these requirements relating to the SYNERGIES Database, the SYNERGIES Marketplace and the SYNERGIES Platform:

All requirements are assessed with a status that is described in the following table:

The requirements analysis has been concluded in WP2 task 2.1 and is used as input for this task (D2.1 Stakeholder high-level requirements). The following paragraphs group these requirements relating to the SYNERGIES Database, the SYNERGIES Marketplace and the SYNERGIES Platform:

All requirements are assessed with a status that is described in Table 1. Description of status of requirements.

In Table 2. Summary of implemented requirements., we present a summary of the state of implementation of the requirements for the database, marketplace, and platform; with 45% addressed requirements out of the 46 relevant requirements.

Status	Description of the status
Not yet addressed	The requirement is acknowledged and will be fulfilled, but the current architectural detail is insufficient to provide a definitive solution. This is due to ongoing decisions regarding technology choices and dependencies on deliverables from other Work Packages (WPs), which are expected to provide the necessary input for a complete architectural response
Not relevant for architecture	This requirement addresses the process or content and has no impact on the architecture
Partly met, not yet fully addressed	The architecture contains some aspects of this requirement, but is not detailed enough yet in order to fully satisfy all aspects of the requirement
Unclear whether architecture relevant	It is unclear at the moment whether this requirement has an impact on the architecture ¹
Does not comply	The current architecture is in resistance to this requirement
Addressed	The requirement is covered in the current architecture

Table 1. Description of status of requirements.

Requirement	Number	Addressed	Partly met	Not relevant	Not yet
Database	30	4	4	9	13
Marketplace	4	1	0	1	2
Platform	27	15	2	5	5

Table 2. Summary of implemented requirements.

3.1 SYNERGIES Database Requirements

The requirements in Table 3. Assessment of Database requirements defined in WP2, were collected in WP2 concerning the scenario database, and in the table we track which requirements are already addressed. Detailed information about the requirements can be found in D2.1, chapter 3.1.

Requirement	Status	Comment
Req_01 Interoperable Scenario Database Development	Addressed	The APIs are defined and it is considered interoperable scenario databases.
Req_02 Harmonization of Scenario-Based Safety Assessment	Not yet addressed	
Req_03 Comprehensive Scenario Coverage	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_04 Scenario for Evaluating V2X	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_05 Scenario Selection for Virtual Testing	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_06 Scenario-Based Validation and Testing	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_07 Scenario Database-Driven Evidence Dossier	Not yet addressed	Creation of evidence dossiers
Req_08 Standardized Data Formats and Interfaces	Addressed	Ensure use of standards

Req_09 Data Security and Privacy	Partly met, not yet fully addressed	
Req_10 Scenario export format	Addressed	
Req_11 Additional Scenario export formats	Not yet addressed	
Req_12 Consistent interfaces for object and trajectory	Not yet addressed	
Req_13 Standardized, established output format	Addressed	
Req_14 Scenario space designed for homologation use-cases	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_15 Input data quality	Not yet addressed	Quality assurance framework
Req_16 Support of scenarios from regulatory institutions	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_17 Sources of scenarios	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_18 Traceability, Version Control, and Access Management	Not yet addressed	
Req_19 Dynamic Scenario Adjustment (1)	Not yet addressed	
Req_20 Dynamic Scenario Adjustment (2)	Not yet addressed	
Req_21 Standardized Scenario Definition	Partly met, not yet fully addressed	Compliance history logs
Req_22 Scenario-Based Performance Metrics for Homologation	Not yet addressed	
Req_23 Scenario filtering by regulation and system	Not yet addressed	
Req_24 Suitability of Virtual, track or real-world testing	Partly met, not yet fully addressed	
Req_25 Scenario format support for co-simulation	Not yet addressed	
Req_26 Raw data content processing and storage	Not yet addressed	FAME project
Req_27 Metadata to facilitate scenario retrieval	Partly met, not yet fully addressed	

Req_28 Sensors independent scenarios	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_29 Adapted to local regulation	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_30 AI act compliance + GDPR	Not yet addressed	

Table 3. Assessment of Database requirements defined in WP2.

3.2 SYNERGIES Marketplace Requirements

The requirements in Table 4. Assessment of SYNERGIES Marketplace requirements, were collected in WP2 concerning the marketplace, and in the table we track which requirements are already addressed. Detailed information about the requirements can be found in D2.1, chapter 3.2.

Requirement	Status	Comment
Req_31 AI Tools for adversarial scenario generation	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_32 Guidelines for ground truth generation	Not yet addressed	
Req_33 Identification of critical zones	Not yet addressed	
Req_34 Scenario Export tool	Addressed	

Table 4. Assessment of SYNERGIES Marketplace requirements.

3.3 SYNERGIES Platform Requirements

The requirements in Table 5, were collected in WP2 concerning the platform, and in the table we track which requirements are already addressed. Detailed information about the requirements can be found in D2.1, chapter 3.3.

Requirement	Status	Comment
Req_35 Open-Source or Open-Access License	Addressed	Open Access License
Req_36 Interoperability and Compatibility	Addressed	
Req_37 Scalability and Performance	Addressed	
Req_38 Extensibility and Modularity	Addressed	
Req_39 Versioning and Change Management	Addressed	GitLab
Req_40 Reporting and Analytics	Not yet addressed	

Req_41 Required Standards	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_42 Communication between users and data providers	Not yet addressed	Contact us?
Req_43 Federated architecture	Addressed	
Req_44 Intended users	Addressed	
Req_45 In-Service Monitoring and Reporting (ISMR)	Not yet addressed	
Req_46 Detection of similar scenarios	Not yet addressed	Tool? WP5
Req_47 Assurance of Scenario Usability and Acceptance	Addressed	
Req_48 User Documentation for Platform End-Users	Partly met, not yet fully addressed	Task 7.4
Req_49 Secure Connectivity and Data Management	Addressed	
Req_50 Compliance with National and International Privacy Laws	Addressed	
Req_51 Secure Cloud Hosting	Addressed	
Req_52 Integration with External Data Sources	Addressed	
Req_53 Gap Analysis and Coverage Improvement	Not yet addressed	
Req_54 Open API	Addressed	
Req_55 Open and detailed Guidelines for data tagging	Not relevant for architecture	Addressed
Req_56 Reports to evaluate the effects of regulations and policies	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_57 User Access and Permissions	Addressed	
Req_58 Community Engagement and Collaboration	Partly met, not yet fully addressed	WP8
Req_59 Metadata to facilitate scenario retrieval	Addressed	
Req_60 Government Agencies	Not relevant for architecture	
Req_61 Public Entities	Not relevant for architecture	

Table 5. Assessment of SYNERGIES Platform requirements.

4 NEXT STEPS

In the current milestone, Synergies WP7 partners deliver a first implementation of the Synergies platform.

Further in the project, T7.2 "Test and validation of the scenario platform system" evaluates the platform and will provide valuable inputs to T7.3, which deals with "Scenario platform mitigation plan and improvement". These activities are expected to start now (M18) after this first successful platform release and continue in the year 2026.

As part of these upcoming improvements, we also aim to migrate the platform infrastructure from AWS to an open-source environment in the next release.

Next deliverables relevant to the WP7 Synergies platform:

- D7.3, "SYNERGIES platform release v2" will be the second release of the platform, due M24
- D7.5, "Report on SYNERGIES platform mitigation plan based on continuous platform adaptations", the resulting report from T7.3, due M30.
- Finally, D7.4 "SYNERGIES platform release v3" and D7.6 "User handbook and documentation of the SYNERGIES platform" due in M36 provide the final material regarding the Synergies platform at the end of the Synergies project.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] SYNERGIES_D2.1 Stakeholder high-level requirements_1.0
- [2] SYNERGES_D3.1_Methodology_for_data_quality_assessment_v1.0
- [3] SYNERGIES_D7.1_Report on the SYNERGIES platform architecture and design together with the defined system components_V1.0
- [4] SYNERGIES_D8.1 Evaluation Framework methodology v.1.0
- [5] SYNERGIES Deliverable D10.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan, September 2024.

A. ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

CCAM	Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure, and Environment Executive Agency
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SYNERGIES	Real and Synthetic Scenarios Generated for the Development, Training, Virtual Testing and Validation of CCAM Systems
WP	Work Package